

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ORAL CARE FOR ONCOLOGY PATIENTS

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Abstract

The study evaluated the impact of oral health on the quality of life of oncological patients using the OHIP-14 questionnaire. Results showed that psychosocial aspects, particularly psychological and social disability, were the most affected domains. Male patients and those with head and neck cancers reported significantly poorer outcomes, while a higher number of chemotherapy/radiotherapy courses was associated with greater oral pain. Subjective knowledge of oral care varied but did not significantly influence overall OHRQoL. Comprehensive multidisciplinary oral care is essential to improve patients' well-being.

Keywords: Oral health, Quality of life, Oncological patients, OHIP-14, Chemotherapy, Radiotherapy.

Research Relevance. The aging of the global population is a major factor contributing to the increasing incidence of oncological diseases. Cancer, characterized by its high mortality rate, remains one of the leading causes of death worldwide (7). According to data from the International Agency for Research on Cancer, approximately 18 million new cancer cases are diagnosed annually, with mortality reaching around 9 million deaths per year. Projections suggest that by 2040 this number may rise by as much as 63.4%, reflecting an accelerating trend in the spread of the disease (2). Among the most common non-surgical treatment modalities for cancer are chemotherapy and radiotherapy. Nevertheless, these therapeutic approaches are frequently associated with complications, such as oral mucositis, which significantly impairs patients' quality of life (5). Another frequent complication is xerostomia, or dry mouth, commonly observed in patients undergoing radiation therapy or chemotherapy (6). This adverse effect not only causes severe pain but also compromises essential physiological functions, including swallowing and food intake (5).

Patients receiving chemotherapy and/or radiotherapy are therefore confronted with substantial oral health challenges and complications. Adverse outcomes include oral mucositis, xerostomia, painful ulcerations, and alterations or loss of taste sensation. These manifestations are often highly distressing, severely restricting daily activities such as speaking, eating, and even swallowing saliva, thereby further diminishing overall quality of life. Additionally, such conditions increase the risk of bacterial infections due to disruption of cellular integrity (4). Evidence indicates that appropriate oral mucosa and dental care during oncological treatment can considerably improve patients' quality of life (1).

Research Problem. Oncological patients face specific oral care challenges during treatment.

Chemotherapy and radiotherapy frequently induce complications in both soft and hard oral tissues, which can profoundly affect patients' quality of life. An appropriate oral care routine may reduce the sensation of oral dryness as well as the incidence of mucosal lesions, candidiasis, and other infections. For patients, this is particularly important, as it alleviates oral mucosal pain and ultimately contributes to an improved quality of life (3).

Research Methodology. Research Methods

Participants. The study sample consisted of 115 respondents who participated in the survey. Inclusion criteria required participants to be oncological patients, of legal adult age (18 years or older), and to have voluntarily consented to take part in the study.

Data Collection. Data were collected using a written, self-administered survey. The questionnaire was actively disseminated through the social media platform *Facebook*, specifically within groups dedicated to oncological patients. A quantitative non-probability convenience sampling method was employed.

Instrument. The study employed the OHIP-14 (Oral Health Impact Profile), a shortened and widely used questionnaire designed to assess the impact of oral health on quality of life. In addition, a review of the scientific literature was conducted to compare the findings of the present study with previous research. Relevant sources were identified through searches of academic databases, including Google Scholar, EBSCO, PubMed, and others.

Statistical Analysis. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences), version 24.0. Microsoft Excel 2010 was employed to generate graphical representations. The Kolmogorov–Smirnov test was applied to assess the normality of variable distributions. Parametric tests were used when the assumption of

normality was met, while non-parametric tests were applied in cases where normality was not satisfied.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, including frequency tables and measures of central tendency. Nominal variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while means and standard deviations ($m \pm SD$) were calculated for continuous variables.

Comparisons between groups were conducted using the Student's *t*-test for differences between two groups, and ANOVA for comparisons involving more than two groups. To examine the percentage distributions of nominal variables, cross-tabulations were performed and analyzed using the χ^2 test and Fisher's exact test (for 2×2 contingency tables). Additionally, the Z-test with Bonferroni correction was applied where appropriate.

Associations between variables were evaluated using Spearman's correlation to explore relationships with demographic factors or ordinal variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. The interpretation of correlation strength followed the guidelines proposed by Čekanavičius and Murauskas (2000): very weak (-0.3 to 0.3), weak (0.3 to 0.5 or -0.3 to -0.5), moderate (0.5 to 0.7 or -0.5 to -0.7), and strong (0.7 to 0.9 or -0.7 to -0.9).

Ethical Considerations

Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection. Anonymity was strictly maintained, and confidentiality of the collected information was ensured at all stages of the research process. Respondents were informed about the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their right to withdraw at any point without any consequences.

The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and complied with general ethical standards for research involving human participants (8). No personally identifying information was collected, thereby minimizing potential risks to participants.

The quality of life of oncological patients is closely associated with their oral health

In order to assess the impact of oral health on the quality of life of oncological patients, the OHIP-14 questionnaire was employed and the results were analyzed. The frequency of responses was evaluated using a Likert scale ranging from 0 to 4: never (0), hardly ever (1), occasionally (2), fairly often (3), and very often (4). Oral health-related quality of life was calculated by summing the scores of all 14 items (minimum possible score: 0; maximum possible score: 56). A higher total OHIP-14 score indicated a greater negative impact on quality of life.

Figure 1. Quality of life of oncological patients in relation to oral health, means

When assessing the oral health-related quality of life (OHIP-14) of older adults (see Figure 1), it was found that respondents most frequently experienced psychological disability ($M = 4.70$), social disability ($M = 4.67$), other physical and psychological limitations ($M = 3.90$), psychological discomfort ($M = 3.87$), and physical pain ($M = 3.71$). The least frequently reported impacts were functional limitation ($M = 3.31$) and physical disability ($M = 3.17$).

These findings suggest that oral health problems among older oncological patients primarily affect psychosocial aspects of daily life rather than purely

physical functions. Psychological disability and social disability received the highest scores, indicating that the consequences of impaired oral health extend beyond clinical symptoms to influence self-esteem, social interactions, and overall well-being. Although physical impairments such as functional limitation and physical disability were reported less frequently, the persistent presence of psychological and social challenges highlights the need for a holistic approach to oral care in oncological treatment, integrating both medical and psychosocial support measures.

Table 1.

Assessment of oral health–related quality of life among oncological patients according to demographic and disease-related factors

Factors		Oral health–related quality of life		p-value
		Mean	SD	
Gender	Male	34,00	9,12	0,034*
	Famale	26,70	10,38	
Place of residence	Urban	27,30	10,85	0,946
	Rural	27,46	9,14	
Age	45 m.	26,79	9,88	0,876
	46-60 m.	27,83	10,91	
	61 m. ir daugiau	26,84	10,27	
Education	Secondary	24,20	14,67	0,118
	Vocational	26,91	13,16	
	Higher (college)	31,44	8,83	
	Higher university	26,22	9,62	
Disease site	Head and neck	40,57	13,43	0,014*
	Thoracic	26,04	9,65	
	Abdominal	25,82	10,87	
	Pelvic	32,00	4,55	
	Hematological	20,00	-	
	Other	27,38	10,15	
Chemotherapy/radiotherapy	1-5	26,12	11,90	0,627
	> 5	27,23	9,71	
Surgical treatment	Yes	27,15	10,98	0,733
	No	27,93	8,75	
Chemotherapy	Yes	27,26	10,24	0,846
	No	27,81	12,01	
Radiotherapy	Yes	26,34	11,07	0,218
	No	28,79	9,39	
Immunotherapy	Yes	26,67	13,74	0,816
	No	27,46	9,80	
Other treatments	Yes	26,54	10,04	0,659
	No	27,57	10,61	
Overall		27,34	10,45	---

* - $p < 0,05$;

The overall oral health–related quality of life (OHRQoL) score among oncological patients was 27.34 ± 10.45 . Statistically significant differences were identified with respect to gender: men reported a poorer quality of life (34.00 ± 9.12) compared to women (26.70 ± 10.38) ($t = 2.143$; $df = 113$; $p = 0.034$).

In addition, significant differences were observed across disease sites. Patients diagnosed with head and neck cancer reported the poorest quality of life (40.57 ± 13.43), followed by those with pelvic cancers (32.00

± 4.55). Conversely, the most favorable quality of life was reported by patients with hematological cancers (20.00 ± 0), abdominal cancers (25.82 ± 10.87), and thoracic cancers (26.04 ± 9.65) ($F = 3.001$; $p = 0.014$).

However, no statistically significant differences were found when OHRQoL was evaluated according to place of residence, age, education level, number of chemotherapy/radiotherapy courses, or type of oncological treatment received ($p > 0.05$).

Table 2.

Associations between oral health–related quality of life (OHRQoL), patient age, and the number of chemotherapy/radiotherapy courses among oncological patients

Associations		Age	Chemotherapy/radiotherapy courses
Functional limitation	r	-0,102	-0,057
	p	0,278	0,549
Physical pain	r	0,062	0,207*
	p	0,509	0,029
Psychological discomfort	r	-0,061	-0,086
	p	0,514	0,370
Physical disability	r	0,031	-0,072
	p	0,743	0,449
Psychological disability	r	-0,176	0,014
	p	0,061	0,880
Social disability	r	-0,095	-0,016
	p	0,313	0,864
Other physical and psychological limits	r	-0,134	0,029
	p	0,155	0,763
Overall quality of life	r	-0,095	0,022
	p	0,312	0,820

Note: *r* – Spearman’s correlation coefficient; *p* – statistical significance; $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**).

As shown in Table 2, a greater number of chemotherapy/radiotherapy courses was associated with more frequent experiences of oral cavity–related physical pain ($r = 0.207$; $p = 0.029$). However, patient age and the number of treatment courses did not have a statistically significant impact on overall oral health–related quality of life (OHRQoL) ($p > 0.05$). The present findings indicate that oral health problems in oncological patients predominantly compromise psychosocial functioning, with the highest OHIP-14 mean scores observed for psychological and social disability. This pattern is congruent with prior research suggesting that the impact of oral conditions in cancer care extends beyond physical symptoms to affect self-image, social participation, and emotional well-being. Consistent with the literature, patients with head and neck malignancies reported the poorest oral health–related quality of life (OHRQoL), likely reflecting treatment-related toxicities such as mucositis, dysgeusia, dysphagia, and xerostomia, which cumulatively disrupt eating, speech, and social interaction. The observed gender difference—poorer OHRQoL among men—has also been described

elsewhere and may relate to differential symptom reporting, coping styles, comorbidity profiles, or treatment intensity; however, this requires further study within adequately powered, sex-stratified analyses.

Importantly, a greater number of chemotherapy/radiotherapy courses was associated with more frequent oral cavity–related physical pain, supporting dose- and time-dependent mucosal toxicity mechanisms and highlighting the need for proactive oral care protocols (e.g., mucositis prevention bundles, saliva-sparing strategies, early pain management). By contrast, neither age nor the overall number of treatment courses showed a statistically significant association with aggregate OHRQoL scores, suggesting that the global burden captured by OHIP-14 may be driven more by disease site and specific toxicities than by chronological age per se. Clinically, these results underscore the value of multidisciplinary, preventive oral health support embedded within oncology pathways, particularly for head and neck cancer patients and those undergoing prolonged treatment courses.

Table 3.

Subjective assessment of oncological patients' knowledge about oral care during chemotherapy or radiotherapy according to demographic and disease-related factors (percentages)

Factors		Subjective knowledge of oral care			p
		Poor/No knowledge	Good / very good knowledge	Good / Very good knowledge	
Gender	Male	40	50	10	0,721
	Famale	48,6	37,1	14,3	
Place of residence	Urban	48,3	36	15,7	0,472
	Rural	46,2	46,2	7,7	
Age	45 m.	41,7	45,8	12,5	0,931
	46-60 m.	49,2	37,3	13,6	
	61 m. and more	50	34,4	15,6	
Eduacation	Secondary	60	30	10	0,551
	Vocational	36,4	45,5	18,2	
	Higher (college)	48,1	48,1	3,7	
	Higher university	47,8	34,3	17,9	
Disease site	Head and neck	57,1	14,3	28,6	0,696
	Thoracic	51,5	36,8	11,8	
	Abdominal	36,4	45,5	18,2	
	Pelvic	75	25	0	
	Hematological	0	100	0	
	Other	37,5	45,8	16,7	
Chemotherapy/radiotherapy	1-5				
	> 5				
Surgical treatment	Yes	506	34,5	14,9	0,338
	No	39,3	50	10,7	
Chemotherapy	Yes	43,4	42,4	14,1	0,047*
	No	75	12,5	12,5	

A comparison of oncological patients' self-assessed knowledge about oral care during chemotherapy or radiotherapy (see Table 3) revealed that patients who underwent other treatment modalities were more likely to report poor knowledge (75.0%) compared to those who had chemotherapy (43.4%) ($\chi^2 = 6.120$; $df = 2$; $p = 0.047$). Moreover, patients who received chemotherapy more frequently rated their knowledge as moderate compared to those treated with other modalities.

It was also observed that patients undergoing radiotherapy were more likely to rate their knowledge as poor (57.4%) than those treated with other methods (34.0%) ($\chi^2 = 7.111$; $df = 2$; $p = 0.029$).

However, no statistically significant differences in knowledge assessment were identified when considering gender, place of residence, age, education, or cancer site ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4.

Assessment of oral health-related quality of life (OHRQoL) among oncological patients according to their subjective knowledge of oral care

Factors		Oral health-related quality of life		p
		Mean	SD	
Subjective knowledge of oral care	Poor/No knowledge	27,76	11,67	0,875
	Moderate knowledge	27,20	9,04	
	Good/Very good knowledge	26,25	10,14	

Note: $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

As shown in Table 6, the OHRQoL score of oncological patients who rated their knowledge as poor was 27.76 ± 11.67 , those who rated their knowledge as moderate reported 27.20 ± 9.04 , and those who rated their knowledge as good or very good scored 26.25 ± 10.14 . These findings indicate that oral health-related quality of life was similar regardless of how patients evaluated their own knowledge about oral care during treatment ($F = 0.134$; $p = 0.875$).

Conclusions

1. Oral health significantly influences the quality of life of oncological patients. The strongest negative effects are related to psychosocial aspects—psychological and social disability, discomfort, and oral pain—demonstrating that oral health problems extend beyond physical symptoms to affect emotional well-being and social functioning.

2. Disease site and treatment intensity affect quality of life outcomes. Male patients and those with head and neck or pelvic cancers reported poorer oral health-related quality of life, while a higher number of chemotherapy/radiotherapy courses was associated with more frequent oral pain.

3. Knowledge of oral care remains insufficient and does not directly determine quality of life. Although some patients assessed their knowledge as poor—particularly those undergoing radiotherapy or non-chemotherapy treatments—differences in self-assessed knowledge did not significantly impact overall OHRQoL, highlighting the need for comprehensive multidisciplinary support that combines medical, psychological, and educational interventions.

References

1. Amin M, Khan FR, Allana A, Barolia R, Azam I. Oral health of chemotherapy patients before and after provision of oral hygiene instructions at a tertiary care hospital: pre-post design. *BMC Oral Health*. 2024;24(1):655. doi:10.1186/s12903-024-04093-0
2. Bolton L. Managing oral mucositis in patients with cancer. *Wounds*. 2021;33(5):136–8. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34370681/>
3. Karlsson C, Bohm N, Andersson JS, Finizia C, Almståhl A. Prospective study on health-related quality of life, oral mucositis and oral health during treatment

of head and neck cancer. *BMC Oral Health*. 2024;24(1):697. doi:10.1186/s12903-024-04466-5

4. Kawashita Y, Soutome S, Umeda M, Saito T. Oral management strategies for radiotherapy of head and neck cancer. *Jpn Dent Sci Rev*. 2020;56(1):62–7. doi:10.1016/j.jdsr.2020.02.001

5. Kusiak A, Jereczek-Fossa BA, Cichońska D, Alterio D. Oncological-therapy related oral mucositis as an interdisciplinary problem: literature review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(7):2464. doi:10.3390/ijerph17072464

6. Padure A, Horhat R, Talpos-Niculescu IC, Scheusan R, Anghel MD, Rusu L-C, et al. Oral mucositis in adult cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy: six-month on-treatment follow-up. *J Clin Med*. 2024;13(19):5723. doi:10.3390/jcm13195723

7. Peña-Cardelles JF, Salgado-Peralvo AO, Garrido-Martínez P, Cebrián-Carretero JL, Pozo-Kreilinger JJ, Moro-Rodríguez JE. Oral mucositis: is it present in the immunotherapy of the immune checkpoint PD1/PD-L1 against oral cancer? A systematic review. *Medicina Oral, Patología Oral y Cirugía Bucal*. 2021;26(4):e494–e501. doi:10.4317/medoral.24353

8. World Medical Association. World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki: ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA*. 2013;310(20):2191–4.